

Sea surface temperature and chlorophyll concentration effects on suspended blue mussel *Mytilus* sp. health biometrics in Irish waters, 1992–2022

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ABSTRACT: Over a 30 yr period (1992–2022), suspended blue mussels *Mytilus* sp. in Irish waters exhibited significant declines in biometrics, marked by reductions in wet tissue weight (17%) and condition index, alongside increases in shell:dry tissue and moisture:dry weight ratios (17%). These changes coincided with complex sea surface temperature (SST) dynamics as episodic warming and cooling phases occurred. SST increased overall, with warmer temperatures — particularly minimum and maximum SST — being positively associated with tissue growth and condition at broader spatial scales. Conversely, cooler periods with increased cold days (<10°C), notably 2002–2011, corresponded with elevated moisture:dry weight ratio, indicating stress or nutritional limitation. Chlorophyll concentrations, used as a proxy for food availability, remained relatively stable throughout, although a slight but significant rise in minimum values suggested a potential baseline shift. Importantly, the influence of environmental drivers varied by scale: SST exerted the strongest predictive power when all data were analysed, while at finer spatial resolutions — especially within transitional waters — chlorophyll metrics showed stronger, positive correlations with biometric health. By contrast, northern and coastal sites exhibited negative or mixed chlorophyll relationships, potentially reflecting poor food quality or eutrophic stress. These findings highlight the scale-dependent nature of mussel responses to environmental change, and underscore the need to consider both thermal and trophic drivers when evaluating bivalve health under future climate scenarios.

KEY WORDS: Sea surface temperature · Chlorophyll *a* · *Mytilus edulis* · Ireland

1. INTRODUCTION

The blue mussel *Mytilus* sp. is a cornerstone species of the Irish intertidal and nearshore environment, producing dense clusters which can provide important habitats for other local species. It is a low trophic level food chain source for other marine species (Petraitis & Dudgeon 2020) in both coastal and transitional waters. These water classifications are established by identifying appropriate geographical features in accordance with the Water Framework Directive guidance document 5 (Water Framework Directive 2003), to-

gether with surface salinity criteria, whereby transitional waters are defined as having salinity of <30 ppt, while coastal waters are identified by salinity of >30 ppt. Worldwide, bivalves, including blue mussels, account for 14–16% of the average yearly protein consumed by humans (Masanja et al. 2023). Commercial mussel production is the largest aquaculture industry in Ireland in terms of tonnage, and the third most important economically next to oysters and salmon (BIM 2024). Thus, not only are mussels important from an environmental basis, but they are also of great economic importance to Ireland.

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Mussel shell and tissue growth and body condition are dependent on a variety of factors, such as food availability and the stage of the reproductive cycle. Additionally, these factors are driven by a myriad of factors such as habitat type and location, water salinity and temperature, and can be heavily influenced by anthropogenic impacts in the form of pollution and nutrient introduction (Gallardi 2016, Gallardi et al. 2017, Seuront et al. 2019, Petraitis & Dudgeon 2020, Kamermans et al. 2022, Masanja et al. 2023). With reported declines of intertidal invertebrate species including *Mytilus* sp. around Ireland (Little et al. 2024) and in other Atlantic coastal waters in recent times (Petraitis & Dudgeon 2020, Baden et al. 2021, Padin et al. 2024), it is vital to understand the causes of population decline and to ascertain whether the loss of marine services for dependent species can be prevented.

Bivalves including *Mytilus* sp. are known to be sensitive to water temperature changes (Peruzza et al. 2023), with small deviations from their ideal range potentially leading to stress and detrimental impacts on their physiology (Masanja et al. 2023, Peruzza et al. 2023). Higher temperatures are often considered to be more detrimental than lower temperatures. Temperatures over 25°C and below 10°C, whilst not necessarily leading to mortality, can lead to stress and thus reduced health status (Masanja et al. 2023). Peruzza et al. (2023) found that when subjected to temperatures of 30°C for 30 d (marine heatwave conditions), the Manila clam *Ruditapes philippinarum*, a bivalve, showed reduced energy reserves and changed behaviour and reproduction. The fact that mussels are sessile renders them more susceptible to acute and longer-term changes in temperature: unlike fish species, which can migrate, mussels are unable to relocate to mitigate against adverse temperature or other effects (Wernberg et al. 2016, Melbourne-Thomas et al. 2022, Jacobs et al. 2024, Vlietstra & Thoenen 2024).

Marine heatwaves have been observed in Irish waters, with June 2023 being an example in which the monthly sea surface temperature (SST) was found to be around 4°C higher than average (McCarthy et al. 2023b). Such heatwaves are known to cause physiological stress on *Mytilus* sp., which can lead to reduced growth and even mortality, as observed in French waters during 2018 (Seuront et al. 2019). It is often hypothesised that should the world's waters continue to warm at the current rate, there will be a negative impact on many marine species, including altered physiology, trophic interaction, abundance, survival and distribution, as detailed in a review by Venegas et al. (2023). Petraitis & Dudgeon (2020)

found that as the August water temperature rose in the Gulf of Maine at a rate of 0.085°C yr⁻¹ over the past 2 decades, the abundance of mussels within a defined area decreased and mussel recruitment reduced at a rate of 15.7% yr⁻¹. This, in turn, could lead to the potential simplification of the food web, with far-reaching impacts on the marine biodiversity of an area. Thus, it is vital to understand if these processes are also occurring in Irish waters.

Despite the warming of the world's oceans, it has been found that Ireland's waters have cooled by 0.3°C decade⁻¹ since 2007 as a result of anthropogenic climate change (McCarthy et al. 2023a). This is in keeping with the finding by Yao et al. (2022) that unlike the majority of the world's maritime environment, the Subpolar North Atlantic is projected to have an increased occurrence of marine cold spells in the future in response to a slowdown in the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC), the system of ocean currents that transports a large amount of heat northwards in the Atlantic and heavily influences Irish waters (McCarthy et al. 2015, 2023a). It is expected that a slowdown in the AMOC could lead to lower water temperatures in the subpolar North Atlantic (Bryden et al. 2020). Caesar et al. (2021) noted that the AMOC has already weakened, whilst Rahmstorf (2024) emphasized the underestimated environmental risk of AMOC collapse. In addition to temperature impacts, an AMOC slowdown could directly impact nutrient pathways towards the subpolar North Atlantic (Whitt & Jansen 2020), which would, in turn, alter phytoplankton dynamics and chlorophyll availability, as well as potentially influencing recruitment by transporting larvae further north (Little et al. 2024).

Food availability is also expected to have an influence on *Mytilus* sp. health in Irish waters. *Mytilus* sp. are filter feeders that rely on phytoplankton as their primary food source. Satellite-derived chlorophyll measurements enable real-time, large-scale tracking of phytoplankton biomass, allowing gap filling in areas where *in situ* sampling is not possible, and thus provide insights into food availability quantified through chlorophyll *a* (Casal et al. 2022, Schoeman et al. 2025). Fernández-Tejedor et al. (2022) used satellite-derived chlorophyll concentrations to help develop models to assess areas suitable for mussel cultures.

This study hypothesises that the health of suspension grown *Mytilus* sp. within Irish waters, as measured by shell and tissue weight, tissue moisture content, mussel condition index and shell:dry tissue weight ratio, will vary in response to both mean temperature and temperature ranges as well as chlorophyll concentration and ranges within different salinity regimes (coas-

tal salinity > 30 ppt vs. transitional salinity > 30 ppt). Specifically, we hypothesised that the health metrics of the mussels would decline in areas of increased temperatures associated with climate change. Using biometric data collected from *Mytilus* sp. collected during 1992–2022 from 12 stations in the north, south and west of Ireland as well as associated satellite data for SST and chlorophyll concentrations, this study aims to test this hypothesis.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Biological data collection

Biometric data were collected from suspended *Mytilus* sp. (Fig. 1; Table S1 in the Supplement at www.int-res.com/articles/suppl/meps15054_supp.pdf) in support of pollutant-related environmental and/or food safety legislative monitoring and programmes in Irish

Fig. 1. Sampling locations of suspended *Mytilus* sp. in Irish waters from 1992 to 2022. The map shows a total of 35 suspended mussel sampling stations, 12 of which have a longer-term sampling time series (identified by name and black symbols) used for analyses. Circle markers: coastal locations; triangle markers: transitional waters. Marker colours correspond to different geographic regions

marine waters (e.g. European Union Directive 2006/113/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the quality required of shellfish waters; https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv%3AOJ.L_.2006.376.01.0014.01.ENG&toc=OJ%3AL%3A2006%3A376%3AFULL) on the quality of shellfish waters (Shellfish Water Directive) and under the EU 2023/915 directive by the Irish Marine Institute from 1992–2022. Given that these programmes are risk-based — meaning they occur more frequently in areas where risks such as pollution would have an impact, such as near food production sites — sampling coverage can encompass a wide geographical spread for any given year, resulting in a disparate range of locations.

Approximately 50 *Mytilus* sp. individuals (40–60 mm shell length) were collected per sampling event. For suspended culture populations, mussels were sampled representatively from longlines or trestles. Samples were transported to the laboratory in cool boxes, where they were frozen at temperatures below -18°C . Shell length was measured using calipers. Mussels were opened with a scalpel by cutting the adductor muscle, drained of shell liquid and the soft tissue was excised, rinsed with deionised water to remove debris, and blotted for 30–45 min to remove moisture. The pooled wet tissue and dried shell weights were recorded. Pooled wet tissue samples were homogenised using a mechanical tissue homogeniser ($\geq 3 \times 20$ s intervals at ≥ 2000 rpm) until uniform. Moisture content was determined using an ISO/IEC 17025-accredited protocol. A 0.5–2.0 g aliquot of homogenised tissue was weighed, mitigating for different drying times dependent on the pooled weight of the sample, dried at $104 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 16–24 h, equilibrated in a desiccator and reweighed to determine dry weight. Moisture content was calculated as a percentage of the original wet weight. Analytical performance was monitored using certified referee materials from international proficiency schemes, with data accepted only if the quality control z-score was within ± 2 , thus ensuring consistent methods over the study time period.

To minimise aliasing of seasonal and temporal variations such as spawning periods and natural seasonal temperature fluctuations on the biometrics investigated, only samples collected in autumn (September–November) were considered for inclusion in the study. Each *Mytilus* sp. sampling record contains the number of individuals contained in a pooled sample (generally 20–50 individuals), total pooled shell weight, total pooled tissue wet weight, mean shell length of all individually measured mussels and mean body tissue moisture (%), obtained as described previously, where

available. Statistical analysis was completed to investigate geographical and temporal influences on a subset of 12 locations from the west, north and south of Ireland in both coastal and transitional waters (Fig. 1; Table S1) which were consistently sampled throughout the study period of 1992–2022 to ensure any change in sampling location as a result of different sampling programmes was not a driving force in results. Water temperature and salinity were recorded at the sampling station at the time of collection, serving as the primary physical parameters for this study. Additionally, available satellite data on SST and chlorophyll concentration (used as a proxy for food availability) were used.

2.2. Biological data processing

The biometrics assessed included wet tissue weight (g mm^{-1}), calculated by taking the total wet tissue weight per sample and dividing it by the length of the shell, and shell density (g mm^{-1}), derived using the same method. This length-normalisation approach aimed to provide better comparability between sampling events. Dry tissue weight was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Dry tissue weight} = \left[\frac{(100 - \text{moisture \%})}{100} \right] \times \text{wet tissue weight} \quad (1)$$

This was then used to create the shell:dry tissue weight ratio, allowing the comparison of energy input into either shell or tissue weight, which provides insight into whether the individual is prioritising defence (increased shell) or growth (increased tissue). Condition index was calculated by using the formula:

$$\text{Condition index} = \left(\frac{\text{dry tissue weight}}{\text{cubic length}} \right) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Moisture content was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Moisture} = \left(\frac{\text{moisture \%}}{100} \right) \times \text{wet tissue weight} \quad (3)$$

This was used to create the metric moisture:dry tissue weight ratio, allowing insight into the level of hydration per gram of dry weight over time.

To assess long-term trends in biometrics, SST and chlorophyll concentration over time, both a linear and locally estimated scatterplot smoothing (LOESS) regression model with a smoothing span of 0.7 were applied to the data. Model performance was evaluated using the R^2 and p-value for the linear model, but as the LOESS model does not directly supply these metrics, a pseudo- R^2 statistic was calculated as follows:

$$\text{pseudo-}R^2 = 1 - (\text{RSS} / \text{TSS}) \quad (4)$$

where RSS is the residual sum of squares from the LOESS fit, and TSS is the total sum of squares of the variable around its mean. This pseudo- R^2 provides a measure of the proportion of variation explained by the non-parametric model.

To assess the statistical significance of the observed pseudo- R^2 , a permutation-based approach was used. Specifically, 1000 permutations of the year variable were generated, and the LOESS model and corresponding pseudo- R^2 were recalculated for each permutation. This procedure generated a null distribution of pseudo- R^2 values under the assumption of no temporal structure. The p-value was then computed as the proportion of permuted pseudo- R^2 values greater than or equal to the observed R^2 . All analyses were conducted in R (RStudio version 2023.12.1402), and a fixed random seed (set.seed[123]) was used to ensure reproducibility.

Statistical analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics software version 29, which was used to calculate variable means, standard errors and allow non-parametric tests of Kruskal-Wallis analysis, which allows the comparison between 2 or more groups without the assumption of a normal distribution, and is analogous to the 1-way ANOVA; Spearman rank correlation analyses were used to assess relationships between these biometric variables and both SST and chlorophyll variables (described below) as well within geographical and salinity classes.

2.3. SST data collection

Satellite-derived SST data from the NOAA Optimum Interpolation SST product were used for this study (Huang et al. 2021). Water temperature and salinity information were recorded at the time of each mussel sampling event, but these low-resolution data were not informative of the long-term trend in the water temperatures; therefore, high-resolution (0.25°) satellite data were used. Satellite SST data has been shown to accurately capture SST variability in Irish waters (McCarthy et al. 2023a) and longer-term trends (Fig. 2). To verify that these data were sufficiently accurate for near-coastal work, the satellite SST data closest to a near-coast

meteorological buoy (M4; 55°N , 10°W) and a coastal SST station (Malin Head; 55.37°N , 7.33°W) were compared. Linear scaling between the satellite SST and the near-coast (coastal) SST were calculated as 1.02 (0.85), indicating a close correspondence. The weaker relationship for the coastal station was related to an overestimation of the winter temperatures and underestimation of the summer temperatures, as would be expected for the more offshore-weighted satellite SST. Nonetheless, the ability to extract a complete time series of data close to the mussel sampling sites made these data suitable for this study.

SST data were extracted at the gridpoints closest to the mussel sampling location. Yearly averages along with the yearly minimum, maximum, range (maximum – minimum) and number of cold days (defined as days colder than 10°C) were calculated within the geographical (south, west, north) and salinity classes (coastal, transitional) of the 12-station subset of data. Trend lines and associated statistics were calculated using the same method as for biometric variables. Kruskal-Wallis tests and ad hoc pairwise comparisons were performed to assess for differences in these temperature metrics within geographical regions and salinity classes.

Fig. 2. Linear trends in satellite-derived sea surface temperatures (SST) around Irish waters for the period 1992–2022. Black outline: extended exclusive economic zone claimed around Ireland. Negative trends to the west are indicative of the so-called North Atlantic warming hole (Drijfhout et al. 2012)

2.4. Chlorophyll concentration data collection

Monthly mean satellite-derived chlorophyll concentration data from the Copernicus Global Ocean Biogeochemistry analysis and Forecast product (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00015>) were used for this study. It was not possible to provide any validation of the results, as no *in situ* samples were taken. However, satellite chlorophyll data have been successfully used in Irish waters (Casal et al. 2022). Whilst it is expected that there will be some error in the exact concentration recorded, compared with *in situ* data, the general trend should be maintained (Casal et al. 2022). Data from 2000–2022 were used, as this allowed full satellite coverage of the study area. Monthly data were used to allow a direct comparison to the SST data, with the same methods being used to extract data needed for each location. Temporal trend lines and associated statistics were calculated using the same method as for biometric vari-

ables. Kruskal-Wallis tests and pairwise comparisons were performed to assess for differences in these temperature metrics within geographical regions and salinity classes.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Biometrics

Wet tissue weight exhibited a significant decline over the 30 yr period, decreasing from approximately 0.06 to 0.05 g mm⁻¹, representing a 17% loss in tissue weight (Fig. 3). This trend was supported by both the linear regression ($R^2 = 0.042$, $p = 0.002$) and the LOESS model (pseudo- $R^2 = 0.1$, $p < 0.001$). While the linear model explained a small proportion of the variance, the LOESS fit revealed a more nuanced, nonlinear trajectory, with a gradual decline and variability particularly evident during the late 2000s. Wet tissue

Fig. 3. Wet tissue weight sampled from 1992 to 2022 at *Mytilus* sp. sampling sites in Irish waters, grouped by region (north, south, west) and salinity class (coastal vs. transitional). Linear regression (solid line) and LOESS smoothing (dashed line) illustrate long-term trends, with colour annotating the geographic location and shape indicating the salinity class

weight was highest in the south (0.063 g mm^{-1} ; Table S2), significantly higher than the north (0.043 g mm^{-1} ; Kruskal–Wallis, $p < 0.001$) and west (0.049 g mm^{-1} ; Kruskal–Wallis, $p < 0.001$), with no significant difference between north and west (Kruskal–Wallis, $p = 0.053$). Wet tissue weight was also significantly higher at transitional salinity sites than at coastal ones (Kruskal–Wallis, $p < 0.001$).

Shell density (g mm^{-1}) did not change significantly over time, with both linear and LOESS models yielding p -values above 0.05 (Fig. 4). Spatially, shell density was highest in the south (0.117 g mm^{-1} ; Table S2), significantly higher than in the north (0.088 g mm^{-1} ; Kruskal–Wallis, $p = 0.003$) and west (0.111 g mm^{-1} ; Kruskal–Wallis, $p = 0.036$). Shell density was also significantly higher in transitional sites compared to coastal locations (Kruskal–Wallis, $p < 0.001$).

The shell:dry tissue weight ratio was shown to have increased over time from ~ 7 in 1992 to ~ 11.5 in 2022 according to the LOESS trend (Fig. 5). The linear model also indicated an upward trend ($R^2 = 0.193$), while the LOESS model (pseudo- $R^2 = 0.236$) captured more complex changes, including a period of rapid increase between 2005 and 2015, followed by stabilization or slight decline. Regionally, the west (shell:dry tissue weight ratio of 11.98; Table S2) and north (11.17) had significantly higher values than the south (8.59; Kruskal–Wallis, $p < 0.001$), although they did not differ significantly from each other (Kruskal–Wallis, $p = 0.322$). A smaller but still significant difference was found between salinity classes (Kruskal–Wallis,

$p = 0.032$), whereby coastal sites exhibited a higher ratio than transitional sites.

The moisture:dry weight ratio showed a significant increasing trend (Fig. 6). There was a notable rise from 3.5 to 4.1, representing approximately a 17% increase occurring from around 2002 and 2015. Both linear regression ($R^2 = 0.333$, $p < 0.001$) and LOESS smoothing (pseudo- $R^2 = 0.377$, $p < 0.001$) confirmed this pattern. Regionally, the ratio was highest in the north (4.21; Table S2) and west (4.12), both significantly higher than in the south (3.58; Kruskal–Wallis, $p < 0.001$), with no significant difference between the north and west (Kruskal–Wallis, $p = 0.787$). The moisture:dry weight ratio was also significantly lower in transitional compared to coastal salinity sites (Kruskal–Wallis, $p < 0.001$).

Condition index declined from ~ 5.0 in the early 1990s to below 4.0 in recent years (Fig. 7). This decline was statistically significant according to both linear regression ($R^2 = 0.146$, $p < 0.001$) and LOESS analysis (pseudo- $R^2 = 0.162$, $p = 0.008$). The LOESS model revealed a more rapid decline between 2005 and 2015, followed by a modest recovery. Regionally, condition index was highest in the south (Table S2), significantly greater than in the north (3.27; Kruskal–Wallis, $p < 0.001$) and west (3.95; Kruskal–Wallis, $p = 0.020$). Transitional sites had higher condition index values than coastal counterparts (Kruskal–Wallis, $p < 0.001$).

At finer spatial scales, transitional areas in the south consistently displayed the highest biological performance across all metrics (Table S2). This included

Fig. 4. Same as Fig. 3, but for *Mytilus* sp. shell density

Fig. 5. Same as Fig. 3, but for *Mytilus* sp. shell:dry tissue weight ratio

Fig. 6. Same as Fig. 3, but for *Mytilus* sp. moisture:dry tissue weight ratio

the highest wet tissue weight (0.064 g mm^{-1} ; Table S2), shell density (0.126 g mm^{-1}) and condition index (5.5), all with significant support from Kruskal-Wallis tests. By contrast, coastal north and west sites recorded the lowest biological condition, including the lowest wet tissue weight (0.043 and 0.040 , respectively) and condition index (3.27 and 3.2 , respectively; Table S2). The south coastal areas presented intermediate values. Where no significant pairwise differences were observed, such as between the north and

west for the moisture:dry weight ratio (Kruskal-Wallis, $p = 0.787$) and shell:dry tissue weight ratio (Kruskal-Wallis, $p = 0.322$), this lack of differentiation contributes to the broader interpretation of overlapping ecological conditions in those regions.

Together, these findings demonstrate significant temporal declines in tissue weight, moisture content, shell:dry tissue weight ratios and condition index in mussels over the past 3 decades. LOESS models consistently provided better explanatory

Fig. 7. Same as Fig. 3, but for *Mytilus* sp. condition index

power than linear models, capturing nonlinear shifts, inflection points and periods of rapid change. Spatially, individuals in southern and transitional environments exhibited better biological condition, while northern and coastal populations, particularly northern coastal sites, exhibited persistent signs of poorer health.

3.2. SST changes

Fig. 8A shows that SST at suspended mussel culture sites in Irish waters varied spatially and temporally from 1992 to 2022, with distinct differences between linear trends and LOESS fits. Mean monthly SST was significantly higher in the south than in the north

Fig. 8. Same as Fig. 3, but for trends in annual sea surface temperature (SST) at *Mytilus* sp. sampling sites. (A) Mean; (B) maximum (top) and minimum (bottom); (C) range

or west (Kruskal-Wallis, $p < 0.001$; Table S3), and warmer in transitional than coastal waters (Kruskal-Wallis, $p < 0.001$; Fig. 8A). The linear model indicates a modest but significant SST rise ($\sim 0.2^\circ\text{C}$; $R^2 = 0.05$, $p < 0.01$; Fig. 8A), suggesting long-term warming. In contrast, the LOESS fit ($R^2 = 0.21$, $p < 0.01$) reveals non-linear dynamics: SST showed a mid-period cooling across all regions and salinity classes from 2002 to 2011, followed by a warming phase in which transitional waters warmed more than coastal ones.

Fig. 8B shows yearly SST maxima and minima (1992–2022). Maximum SST increased significantly ($R^2 = 0.05$, $p < 0.001$), but the LOESS trend (pseudo- $R^2 = 0.16$) highlights a 2002–2011 decline followed by a sharp rise, indicating episodic rather than steady warming. Maximum SSTs were significantly cooler in the north than in the south and west, with the south being warmest (Kruskal-Wallis, $p < 0.001$; Table S3). Transitional waters had higher maxima than coastal ones (Kruskal-Wallis, $p = 0.004$). Minimum SST LOESS shows a significant increase ($R^2 = 0.10$, $p < 0.001$), capturing fluctuations missed by the non-significant linear trend. Minimum temperatures were highest in the south and lowest in the north; unlike maxima, coastal waters had higher minima than transitional ones (Fig. 8B; Table S3), suggesting greater annual temperature variability in transitional waters. Winter minima rose after 2017 but remained below the earlier peak ($\sim 7^\circ\text{C}$), while summer maxima increased more sharply (18.7 vs. 17.4°C), indicating more intense summer warming.

Fig. 8C shows a modest SST range increase (linear $R^2 = 0.03$, $p < 0.001$; LOESS pseudo- $R^2 = 0.07$), with

the most notable rise occurring after 2015, likely due to higher summer maxima (Fig. 8B). No significant range differences were found between coastal and transitional waters (Kruskal-Wallis, $p = 0.256$). Within coastal areas, the north had a slightly higher average range (9.4°C) than the south (9.2°C) and west (9.07°C), but not significantly (Kruskal-Wallis, $p > 0.05$); no significant geographic variation was found in transitional waters (Kruskal-Wallis, $p = 0.983$).

Fig. 9 shows the number of cold days (SST $< 10^\circ\text{C}$) per year per site. Both linear ($R^2 = 0.013$, $p = 0.02$) and LOESS (pseudo- $R^2 = 0.20$, $p < 0.001$) trends indicate a significant decline over time, although the LOESS fit reveals an increase during 2002–2011 following an initial drop, aligning with cooler periods in Fig. 8A–C. The south had significantly fewer cold days per year (76 ± 2.3) than the north (135 ± 2.25) and west (117 ± 1.6) ($p < 0.001$), while coastal sites had slightly more than transitional ones (99.9 ± 2.5 vs. 92 ± 2.5 ; $p = 0.032$). The largest yearly variation in number of cold days occurred in the south, with less pronounced variation in the west and north.

3.3. Chlorophyll concentration over time

Overall, the yearly mean chlorophyll concentrations showed no significant change over time, with both linear and LOESS lines producing p-values higher than the 0.05 cutoff (Fig. 10A; linear $p = 0.096$, LOESS = 0.5). Figure 10B documents the yearly maximum and minimum chlorophyll concentrations observed over the same time period. The minimum values were found

Fig. 9. Same as Fig. 3, but for number of cold days, defined as those with a sea surface temperature lower than 10°C , per year at suspended *Mytilus* sp. sampling sites

Fig. 10. Same as Fig. 3, but for trends in annual chlorophyll concentration at *Mytilus* sp. sampling sites from 2000 to 2022. (A) Mean; (B) maximum (top) and minimum (bottom); (C) range

to have a small but significant increase on a temporal basis, with both linear and LOESS analysis producing $p < 0.01$ and $R^2 = 0.13$. The maximum yearly value was deemed stable (linear, $p = 0.54$; LOESS, $p = 0.234$), potentially suggesting a slight shift in the baseline chlorophyll levels. Despite this, the yearly range of chlorophyll values showed no significant temporal change (linear, $p = 0.175$; LOESS, $p = 0.086$; Fig. 10C).

A clear geographic separation in chlorophyll metrics across regions was evident (Fig. 10A–C). Kruskal-Wallis tests and Dunn's post hoc analyses indicate significant differences among the north, south and west regions for all chlorophyll variables (Kruskal-Wallis, $p < 0.001$). The south consistently exhibited the highest chlorophyll concentrations, followed by the north, with the west showing the lowest (Table S4). For the yearly chlorophyll mean, the south (mean = 4.03 mg m^{-3}) had significantly higher values than both the north (3.25 mg m^{-3} ; $p = 0.016$) and the west (1.40 mg m^{-3} ; $p < 0.001$), and the north was also significantly higher than the west ($p < 0.001$). Similar patterns were observed for other chlorophyll metrics (Table S4), with all pairwise regional differences significant (Kruskal-Wallis, $p < 0.01$). Salinity class also influenced chlorophyll levels, with transitional waters exhibiting significantly higher concentrations than

coastal waters across all metrics (Kruskal-Wallis, $p < 0.001$). Specifically, the yearly range was nearly 3 times greater (8.21 vs. 3.14), and the maximum concentration was more than double (10.2 vs. 4.56) in transitional waters than in coastal waters (Table S4).

3.4. SST and chlorophyll relationships

Across all 12 stations, several significant correlations were found between SST and chlorophyll concentrations (Table 1). With the exception of range SST, all SST metrics have significant correlations with the chlorophyll metrics; minimum SST has the strongest such correlation. These results suggest that warmer SSTs are linked to both higher baseline and peak chlorophyll levels across broad spatial scales (Table 1).

Regionally, fewer consistent patterns were observed (Table 1). In the south, weak negative relationships emerged between SST and chlorophyll. The north showed stronger negative associations, particularly involving SST range. In the west, chlorophyll levels tended to increase with warmer temperatures, while a greater SST range was linked to reduced chlorophyll levels. Coastal waters showed few clear relationships, with only slight links between chloro-

Table 1. Spearman rank correlation between sea surface temperatures (SST) and chlorophyll concentrations (chl) at sites of *Mytilus* sp. Sampling in Irish waters in different geographical regions (north, south and west) and different salinity classes (transitional and coastal) from 1992 to 2022. ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$. Empty cells: no significant correlation detected

	Chlorophyll concentration			
	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range
Full subset sample (n = 216)				
Mean SST	0.228**	0.233**	0.206**	0.184**
Minimum SST	0.338**	0.331**	0.305**	0.284**
Maximum SST	0.137*	0.147*	0.132*	
Range SST				
South (n = 127)				
Mean SST				
Minimum SST				
Maximum SST		-0.16*		
Range SST		-0.168*		
North (n = 51)				
Mean SST				
Minimum SST				-0.356*
Maximum SST	-0.33**		-0.305**	-0.324*
Range SST	-0.352*		-0.309*	-0.317*
West (n = 37)				
Mean SST		0.285*		
Minimum SST	0.294*			
Maximum SST				
Range SST				-0.263*
Coastal (n = 99)				
Mean SST		0.174*		-0.164*
Minimum SST		0.21**		
Maximum SST				
Range SST				
Transitional (n = 118)				
Mean SST		0.295**		
Minimum SST		0.316**		

phyll and SST (Table 1). In contrast, transitional waters showed strong and consistent associations, with warmer and more variable SST conditions corresponding to higher minimum chlorophyll levels. Overall, broad-scale patterns were clearer than those at regional or salinity-specific levels, likely due to local variability and narrower temperature ranges.

3.5. Relationships between SST variables, chlorophyll variables and biological metrics

Multiple Spearman correlations examined links between SST, chlorophyll and biological metrics (Table 2). Minimum SST was a strong positive predictor of wet tissue weight and moderately correlated with condition index, while negatively correlating with the moisture:dry weight ratio and shell:dry tissue weight

ratio. The number of cold days also correlated negatively with condition index and shell:dry tissue weight ratio, and positively with the moisture:dry weight ratio. However, many chlorophyll measures had no significant links to biological traits (Table 2).

In the southern region, maximum SST was negatively correlated with wet tissue weight (Table 2). Number of cold days was negatively correlated with condition index and wet tissue weight. Chlorophyll mean and maximum were positively correlated with wet tissue weight, shell density and condition index (Table 2). In the northern region, SST metrics generally showed no significant correlations with biological metrics except for minimum SST, which was negatively correlated with shell density and wet tissue weight (Table 2). Chlorophyll levels were negatively correlated with shell density and condition index.

In the west, SST variables had limited influence, while chlorophyll metrics dominated correlations (Table 2). Negative relationships were found between chlorophyll mean and wet tissue weight and between chlorophyll maximum and condition index (Table 2). Notably, minimum chlorophyll showed stronger correlations than maximum chlorophyll in this region.

When grouped by salinity class, chlorophyll metrics show a higher number of significant correlations to biological metrics than do SST metrics. (Table 2). Coastal areas showed consistent negative correlations between chlorophyll and biological condition. By contrast, transitional zones generally showed positive associations (Table 2). Thermal effects within salinity zones were less pronounced. In coastal areas, mean SST was positively correlated with wet tissue weight and condition index and negatively correlated with moisture:dry weight ratio (Table 2). Conversely, minimum SST was negatively correlated with moisture:dry weight ratio and maximum chlorophyll was positively correlated with condition index in transitional zones.

In north coastal sites, SST influences were minimal, while chlorophyll variables were the dominant drivers. Condition index was negatively correlated with both chlorophyll maximum and minimum, while shell density showed similar negative correlations with chlorophyll maximum and range (Table 2). Additionally, the moisture:dry weight ratio was negatively correlated with increasing chlorophyll (Table 2). In south transitional sites, both SST and chlorophyll metrics were significantly correlated with biological indicators (Table 2). Maximum SST was negatively correlated with condition index and positively associated with shell:dry tissue weight ratio and moisture:dry weight ratio. Chlorophyll variables were significantly corre-

Table 2. Spearman rank correlation between biometric variables and both sea surface temperature (SST) and chlorophyll concentration (chl) at sites of *Mytilus* sp. Sampling in Irish waters in different geographical regions (north, south and west) and salinity classes (transitional and coastal) from 1992 to 2022. **p < 0.01; *p < 0.05. Empty cells: no significant correlation detected

Biological variable	Data source	SST				Cold days	Chl			
		Mean	Max.	Min.	Range		Mean	Max.	Min.	Range
Wet tissue weight (g mm ⁻¹)	All data (n = 216)	0.263**	0.72**	0.595**	0.292**	-0.221**	0.159	0.132*	0.131*	0.159**
	South (n = 127)		-0.211*	-0.202*		0.188*	0.325**	0.388**		0.413**
	North (n = 51)			-0.277*				-0.388	-0.355*	-0.375**
	West (n = 37)						-0.358*	-0.39*		
	Coastal (n = 99)	0.269**				-0.298**	-0.304**	-0.319**	-0.262*	-0.311**
	Transitional (n = 118)						0.44**	0.485**		0.514**
	North, coastal (n = 51)			-0.277*				-0.388**	-0.355*	-0.375**
	South, coastal (n = 36)		-0.419*							
	South, transitional (n = 91)					0.232	0.382**	0.478**		0.512**
	West, coastal (n = 11)						-0.648*	-0.733*		-0.745*
West, transitional (n = 26)										
Shell density (g mm ⁻¹)	All data (n = 216)	0.168**			0.179**					
	South (n = 127)			-0.221**	0.174*		0.431**	0.39**	0.185*	0.394**
	North (n = 51)			-0.354**				-0.386**		-0.385**
	West (n = 37)						0.388*		0.38*	
	Coastal (n = 99)						-0.243*	-0.289**	-0.233*	-0.291**
	Transitional (n = 118)			-0.25**			0.31**	0.227*		0.23*
	North, coastal (n = 51)			-0.354**		0.28*		-0.386**		-0.385**
	South, coastal (n = 36)			-0.311*						
	South, transitional (n = 91)			-0.203*			0.548**	0.43**		0.441**
	West, coastal (n = 11)									
West, transitional (n = 26)										
Moisture: dry weight ratio	All data (n = 216)	-0.205**		-0.32**		0.18**	-0.21**	-0.241*		-0.265**
	South (n = 127)			-0.221**	0.174*		-0.256*	-0.3**		-0.332**
	North (n = 51)							0.3*	0.316*	
	West (n = 37)		0.221*		0.216*	-0.177*	0.512**		0.511**	
	Coastal (n = 99)	-0.228*	-0.228*			0.219*	0.292**	0.291**	0.298**	0.275**
	Transitional (n = 118)			-0.292**	0.306**		-0.372**	-0.456**		-0.496**
	North, coastal (n = 51)							0.3	0.316	
	South, coastal (n = 36)									
	South, transitional (n = 91)		0.256*		0.252*					0.353**
	West, coastal (n = 11)									-0.271
West, transitional (n = 26)						0.538**		0.566**		
Shell:dry tissue weight ratio	All data (n = 216)			-0.335**	0.198**	0.199**				
	South (n = 127)			-0.221**	0.174*		0.283**	0.231*	0.213*	0.214*
	North (n = 51)									
	West (n = 37)						0.388*		0.38*	
	Coastal (n = 99)	-0.237*		-0.212*		0.278**				
	Transitional (n = 118)			-0.364**	0.326**					
	North, coastal (n = 51)									
	South, coastal (n = 36)		0.441**		0.381*					
	South, transitional (n = 91)	0.34**	0.262*	-0.221*	0.303**		0.492**	0.378**	0.274*	0.36**
	West, coastal (n = 11)									
West, transitional (n = 26)								0.448*		
Condition index	All data (n = 216)	0.229**		0.271**		-0.218**	0.192	0.207**		0.217**
	South (n = 127)	-0.264**	-0.348**		-0.258**	0.243**	0.393**	0.437**		0.471**
	North (n = 51)							-0.441**	-0.356	-0.424**
	West (n = 37)						-0.439	-0.356		
	Coastal (n = 99)	0.276**				-0.296**	-0.348**	-0.364**	-0.322**	-0.352**
	Transitional (n = 118)		-0.219		-0.27		0.472**	0.529**		0.568**
	North, coastal (n = 51)							-0.441**	-0.356	
	South, coastal (n = 36)		-0.576**		-0.484**					
	South, transitional (n = 91)	-0.257	-0.292**			0.311**	0.377**	0.466**	-0.249	0.517**
	West, coastal (n = 11)						-0.733	-0.77**		-0.782**

lated with all biological metrics, with chlorophyll range showing consistent and significant associations across all biological variables. Generally, chlorophyll maximum had stronger correlation coefficients than chlorophyll minimum, indicating that both thermal stress and productivity were key factors influencing mussel health in this region (Table 2).

By contrast, south coastal sites exhibited signs of thermal stress without evidence of chlorophyll influence. Condition index was strongly and negatively correlated with maximum SST and positively correlated with the shell:dry tissue weight ratio. No chlorophyll metrics were significantly correlated with any biological metric in this subregion, highlighting the primary role of temperature stress (Table 2). The west coastal region showed no significant associations between shell density, moisture:dry weight ratio or shell:dry tissue weight ratio and SST variables. However, strong correlations were observed between chlorophyll metrics and biometrics. Wet tissue weight was negatively associated with chlorophyll mean, maximum and range, while condition index was also negatively correlated with chlorophyll mean, maximum and range (Table 2). It should be noted, however, that due to the small sample size in this subregion, these findings should be interpreted cautiously. In the west transitional sites, few significant relationships were observed. Chlorophyll mean and minimum were positively correlated with moisture content and the latter was positively correlated with shell:dry tissue weight ratio. No significant associations were found between thermal metrics and biological indicators in this region (Table 2).

4. DISCUSSION

Overall, this study has shown that suspended *Mytilus* sp. individuals in Irish waters experienced a long-term biological decline between 1992 and 2022, as indicated by reductions in both wet tissue weight and condition index. Wet tissue weight was observed to have declined 28% from 2007 to 2011, with an overall reduction of 17% over the study period (Fig. 3). Consecutively, shell weight was found to have no significant change over time (Fig. 4). This led to an increase in the shell:dry tissue weight ratio (Fig. 5), reflecting both a decline in tissue weight and rise in the moisture:dry weight ratio and indicating a shift in energy allocation from tissue growth to shell production over time. The 17% increase in the moisture:dry weight ratio (Fig. 6) is indicative of poor health and potentially an indicator of starvation (Lucas & Beninger

1985). The condition index of the *Mytilus* sp. was also seen to decline over time, falling from ~6 to ~4 (Fig. 7).

The lack of significant change in shell density despite a reduction in condition index suggests that overall mussel condition is more closely linked to tissue growth than to shell development. The shell is formed by the organism through biologically controlled calcium carbonate deposition from seawater. This occurs even under low food availability (Alunno-Bruscia et al. 2001), whereas tissue represents the current metabolic and reproductive state of the individual (Gallardi 2016, Gallardi et al. 2017) and can vary more rapidly with environmental conditions than shell growth. This would create a higher shell:dry tissue weight ratio in lower-quality individuals. The present study also supports the findings of Gallardi (2016), who noted that the loss of dry tissue weight coincided with an increase in water content (Fig. 6).

Segregation into geographic location and salinity classes suggests that *Mytilus* sp. in southern waters exhibit healthier metrics; that is, lower moisture:dry tissue weight and shell:dry tissue weight ratios and higher wet tissue weight and condition index than those from the north and west. Individuals in transitional waters return healthier metrics than coastal animals. Kautsky et al. (1990) found that salinity has a significant impact on the growth of blue mussels, which may partly explain the differences observed between coastal and transitional water shell densities in this study. pH-related differences in coastal and transitional waters may also have had an impact on the calcifying ability of the individuals and thus on shell growth (McGrath et al. 2019). Ocean acidification (i.e. reductions in pH) has been shown to lead to an increased propensity toward shell brittleness (Knights et al. 2020); however, this type of analysis is outside the scope of the study and current data availability.

Mytilus sp. primarily feed on organic particles (4–20 μm), mainly phytoplankton (primarily unicellular algae), with some detrital material of lower food quality (Aas et al. 2015). Transitional areas, being closer to shore, are likely to receive higher nutrient input from surface water runoff and river discharge. While *in situ* data on potential food sources for the sampled individuals was not available, it is generally accepted that areas with higher food concentrations support better condition and growth rates in *Mytilus* sp. (Kamermans et al. 2022). Satellite-derived chlorophyll data (a proxy for food) showed no significant temporal change in mean chlorophyll concentration. However, there was a small but statistically significant increase in minimum chlorophyll concentration, suggesting a potential upward shift in the baseline (Fig. 10). It is important to

note that chlorophyll concentration alone does not necessarily indicate food quality or suitability for *Mytilus* sp. Kruskopf & Flynn (2006) found that the relationship between chlorophyll and carbon content varies across phytoplankton species. This suggests that nutrient quality and suitability for *Mytilus* sp. may depend on the specific planktonic species present — an aspect not assessed in this study.

In both the geographical and salinity classifications, the areas which had the highest monthly and yearly mean temperature also have biological metrics indicative of healthier mussel populations. This is contrary to other studies that have found that an increase in temperature leads to reduced health (Gabbott & Bayne 1973, Almada-Villela 1984) and, in some cases, such as that observed in 2018 in France after a heatwave, mass mortality in the mussel population (Seuront et al. 2019). Bayne (1976) found that the optimal conditions for mussel shell and tissue growth are in the range of 10–20°C, with Almada-Villela et al. (1982) finding that the growth of mussel individuals increased logarithmically between 3 and 20°C, but above 20°C, the rate went sharply into decline. The water temperatures observed during this study did not often exceed this 20°C threshold (Fig. 8), meaning that the growth of the sampled individuals should increase as the SST warms. Whilst direct growth rates were not measured, there was a general increase in wet tissue weight and condition index during times of higher temperatures. It should be noted that genetic identification of individuals was not possible during this study, so it remains unclear whether individuals from different areas have distinct genetic heritages. Populations sampled could include *M. edulis* and *M. galloproviialis* (the latter being traditionally a warmer water species), as well as hybrids at different locations (Gosling et al. 2008), which may influence biometric indices due to different environmental tolerances. This possibility warrants further investigation.

The observed sharp decline in SST during the late 2000s is consistent with the decrease in Irish water temperatures since a peak in 2007 at a rate of 0.3°C decade⁻¹ as per McCarthy et al. (2023a). Whilst receiving less attention than warming temperatures and heatwaves, cooling events are also known to have impacts on the biological system. These reduced temperatures could lead to changes in the marine system, such as species range shifts, habitat loss and mortality (Schlegel et al. 2021), which in turn could have an impact on mussel health. However, following this decline, there was an increase in the mean temperature as well as in the minimum, maximum and range of SST observed within the study sites (Fig. 8). Figure

9 shows that not only have the mean, minimum, maximum and range of SSTs changed over the duration of the study, but there has also been an observed change in the number of cold days (defined as days below 10°C, which is the temperature limit below which *Mytilus* sp. become cold-stressed; Bayne 1976), indicative of length of time water temperatures are at a level at which individuals may become stressed.

The most rapid increase in the moisture:dry tissue weight ratio occurs during a time when the overall temperature is seen to decline (Figs. 6 & 8). This is reflected in the negative correlation between both the mean and minimum SST and the moisture:dry tissue weight ratio (Table 2), indicating that cooler temperatures may potentially negatively impact the health of *Mytilus* sp. in Irish waters. This is further supported by correlations between the number of cold days and all biological metrics except shell density (which was found not to change over time) as well as with the condition index (Table 2), using all station data as well as within the segregated south, coastal and south transitional grouping. The south was found to have the highest variability in the number of cold days throughout the study, and thus, it is likely that this is why the relationship is strongest in this region. The positive correlations between the moisture:dry weight ratio, condition index and chlorophyll metrics at the large scale suggest that *Mytilus* sp. thrive in warmer waters with more abundant chlorophyll within our study locations.

A clear hierarchy in environmental drivers of *Mytilus* sp. biometric traits is evident. At broad scales (all locations), SST strongly promotes tissue growth and condition, reflecting its fundamental role in physiological processes (Table 2). However, this thermal influence diminishes at finer spatial scales, at which food availability, indicated by chlorophyll concentration, becomes more dominant. This suggests that resource availability may override temperature effects under certain local conditions, or that the changes in temperature are minimal in the more local area. This observation may also be a result of reduced sampling size at finer scales making the correlations less reliable, highlighting the need for further study. Within the south transitional, where sample sizes were the largest, temperature relationships are still present (Table 2).

The range in SST was seen to markedly increase in recent years (Fig. 8), suggestive of a higher level of seasonality. This is evident from the widening gap between minimum and maximum temperatures in Fig. 8, driven by an increase in maximum tempera-

tures. These trends suggest warmer summers in later years, whilst winter temperatures have remained relatively stable. This trend is further evidenced by the known occurrence of marine heat waves around Ireland in recent years (McCarthy et al. 2023b, Jacobs et al. 2024). Strong or increased seasonality can have impacts on the marine realm, with an increased chance of species' thermal limits being exceeded, but also a potential movement of warmer-water species into more northern areas, which may have an impact on the planktonic species or energy content for species feeding on them, such as *Mytilus* sp. Clarke et al. (2023) documented a shift in planktonic species abundance present in Irish waters over time, with a reduction in dinoflagellates in some areas.

Little et al. (2024) suggest that in Lough Hyne on the southern Irish coast, mussel populations show increased recruitment during colder winter scenarios. This could be a result of coupling with the planktonic bloom, whereby colder winters are associated with stronger blooms (Lewandowska et al. 2014), and thus higher recruitment and higher food availability for growing mussels. However, Folmer et al. (2014) showed that higher recruitment in some bivalves was proposed to be attributed to mild winters and warm spring conditions. Both the results of Folmer et al. (2014) and Little et al. (2024) would be suggestive that a range of temperatures throughout the year (as long as they do not cross the extremes) is important for mussel growth. In our study, of all the sampled areas, the southern mussels showed the best condition-related metrics. It is also true that despite having temperatures below the 10°C lower threshold for growth, the south has the highest minimum temperatures, and thus the logarithmic growth model suggested by Almada-Villela et al. (1982) would predict better growth than in the north regions, where the temperatures are lower. It is also the case that the south has higher maximum temperatures than the north and west, but again, generally within the optimal growth threshold of 10–20°C. Therefore, these areas would be expected to produce larger mussels which undergo less thermal stress and thus should produce more tissue and have a lower moisture content, as observed here (Table 2). Overall, the tissue content and condition index have been seen to decrease in the past 10 yr in all stations (Fig. 2) as the temperature and temperature range increase. It is possible that this implied increased seasonality has a potential role to play in the organism's development. In the North Sea (north of Scotland), a large number of species live at the edge of their thermal range (Smale et al. 2019,

Jacobs et al. 2024). There, heatwave events (and implied general warming) are believed to have caused a decline in the dominant zooplankton species during the summers of 2018–2022, which may have also had an impact on the quality of food that is available for *Mytilus* sp. (Semmour et al. 2023) as a result of thermal stress. Should something similar occur in Irish waters, it could lead to a change in the food availability for *Mytilus* sp., and this could have detrimental impacts such as reduced ability to produce tissue and increased stress markers like the moisture:dry tissue weight ratio.

The decrease in tissue weight (g mm^{-1}) coincides with the stabilization of the moisture:dry weight ratio in the study. This observation potentially suggests that once *Mytilus* sp. reach a certain moisture threshold in their bodies, they may lose the ability to effectively grow tissue. Should this be the case, it may result from depleted energy stores within the individual due to starvation, which has been linked to increased moisture (Gallardi et al. 2017). Within such a situation, the *Mytilus* sp. may not be receiving high enough energy inputs to maintain body condition.

The timing of the observed initial cooling event in mean SST coincides with the finding that the AMOC was seen to decline sharply around 2009–2010 (McCarthy et al. 2015) at a period during which the condition of *Mytilus* sp. began to decline. A slowdown in the AMOC (Caesar et al. 2018, Rahmstorf 2024) could potentially lead to further consequences for mussel health status beyond water temperature changes alone. Whitt & Jansen (2020) reported that a slowdown in ocean currents results in reduced northward water movement, which is expected to lead to a reduced nutrient flow in a northward direction, resulting in reduced productivity in more northern latitudes. It is proposed that this situation could have an impact on food availability, given that Irish coastal phytoplankton composition is shaped by ocean currents and seasonal variations in light, nutrients, salinity, temperature and other factors (Clarke et al. 2023). With the structure of the planktonic population impacting energy and nutrient availability, this would be expected to have a knock-on effect on condition and growth indices (Kamermans et al. 2022), which are shown to be lower in northern sites than southern sites, where this potential nutrient shift may have a lesser impact. It is also the case that different areas around Ireland have different plankton community structures and bloom timings, with the southern bloom occurring about 1 mo earlier than the west (Clarke et al. 2023). This difference in timing could in

itself have an impact on the health of the mussels. These patterns are connected to SST, backed up by the fact that mean SSTs around Ireland vary latitudinally, with temperatures in the south 0.4°C warmer than the west, and temperatures in the west 0.6°C warmer than those in the north (Fig. 2). However, extreme high SSTs to the north are dissimilar from the west and south. Southern and western maximum annual SSTs converge, and are on average only 0.2°C different, indicating a common driver. However, maximum annual SSTs in the north are on average 1.4°C (1.6°C) lower than in the west (south), indicating a different driver of extreme warmth in the north, potentially related to the larger Atlantic influence on the shelf in this location (Porter et al. 2018). Should the aforementioned change in nutrient input arise, the expected stress caused by the cooler temperatures and longer cold periods in the late 2000s, followed by increased yearly temperature variability and potentially altered food availability, may potentially influence the elevated moisture content, which has been linked to starvation (Gallardi et al. 2017). This was observed during this study by reduced condition index and tissue growth in the studied individuals, particularly in the north.

Future climate change scenarios and projections suggest that bivalve populations may face a variety of deleterious health impacts. Altered nutrient inputs, potential impacts on primary productivity and food availability as a suspected consequence of changes in the AMOC may influence moisture content. Impacts on the general settlement pattern of mussels (Little et al. 2024) are noted as being possible as a result of planktonic larvae being carried further north by changes in ocean circulation. Padin et al. (2024) documented changes in upwelling events in Galician waters, which appear to be due to climate change impacts. These changes were linked to a significant decline (-148 t yr^{-1}) in wild mussel seed particularly since 2012, along with decreased egg production over mussel lifetime. This marked decline in seed from 2012 onwards is noteworthy, given that the timing broadly concurs with tissue decline and increased SST yearly range in Irish waters (Figs. 4 & 7). Recent data in Ireland indicate that seed production in Irish waters has also fallen in recent years (Chopin 2024). This could be suggestive of a large-scale driver acting over an extended area—such as current regime change, food shifts, temperature changes and water chemistry alteration over time, as discussed above—and merits further study.

Contrary to the initial hypothesis that rising SSTs would negatively impact mussel health, our results

show that warmer conditions were associated with improved indicators, while health declines coincided with cooler periods. This pattern may be a reflection of the fact that Irish coastal waters rarely exceed the critical upper thermal threshold of $\sim 20^\circ\text{C}$ for *Mytilus* sp. but frequently fall below 10°C , meaning that mussel populations there are more often constrained by cold stress than heat stress. This suggests that cold spells and cooling phase changes have had the greatest negative impact on suspended *Mytilus* sp. populations over the past 3 decades. While we cannot conclusively show that this is linked to the AMOC, there were changes within the AMOC during this time which may have influenced both the temperature and food source for the *Mytilus* sp. If suspension-grown mussels, which are considered to be potentially the mussels least impacted by environmental change, have been impacted to this degree, then it is reasonable to assume natural intertidal mussel populations may also be experiencing reduced health and potentially lower survivorship. While outside of the scope of this study, it is imperative that we further our understanding of future climate change scenarios which may impact *Mytilus* sp. Further research would benefit from wider supporting information such as population density, seed availability (Padin et al. 2024), carrying capacities of water bodies, food availability and structure and the complexities of parasitic loads. Consideration of climate buffering capacity and water chemistry changes (Knights et al. 2020), alongside regional-scale influences of AMOC scenarios, would greatly enhance our understanding of their multi-faceted influences on overall ecosystem health and associated impacts to ecosystem services in Irish waters.

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